

Precipitation occurred at pH 9.04, 9.00, 7.00 and 7.90 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} aspartate systems respectively.

Fig. 2. pH titration curves: (A) 1×10^{-3} g-mol KNO₃ and 1.25×10^{-3} g-mol aspartic acid, (B₁-B₄) 5×10^{-4} g-mol Co(ClO₄)₂, ZnSO₄, NiSO₄ and CuSO₄ respectively, besides the same constituents as in (A).

Formation of 1 : 2 metal-aspartate complexes :

The reaction taking place in the formation of 1 : 2 aspartate complexes can be represented as

The values of *n* were calculated⁴ from equation (6),

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - a/b \Delta[T Asp]}{[C]} = n - 2a/b \quad (6)$$

The values of *n* are less than 4 in all these systems. Assuming the values of *n* to be 4, the equilibrium constant (*K*_{1:2}) for the reaction, $M^{2+} + 2H_2 Asp \rightleftharpoons C_{1:2} + 4H^+$ have been calculated (Table 1).

The reaction due to the addition of monosodium aspartate to the metal ion (Fig. 3) can be represented as

Fig. 3. pH titration curve: (A) 1×10^{-3} g-mol KNO₃, (B₁-B₄) 5×10^{-4} g-mol Co(ClO₄)₂, ZnSO₄, NiSO₄ and CuSO₄ respectively, besides the same constituents as in (A).

It has been observed from experiment 1 that the complex C exists in the pH range of this experiment (below 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio). The equilibrium

constants (*K*_s) for reaction (7) were calculated as before by using the equations,

$$[T H_2 Asp] = p [H Asp^-] + [C] \quad (8)$$

$$[C] = [H^+] + r [H Asp^-] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } [T H_2 Asp] = [H^+] + [H Asp^-] (p+r) \quad (10)$$

where, $p = 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} + \frac{k_3}{[H^+]} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2}$;

$$r = \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} + \frac{2[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} - \frac{k_3}{[H^+]}$$

and are recorded in Table 1.

It can be shown that $K = K_s \times k_2$. The values of *K* thus calculated by substituting the values of *K*_s and *k*₂ in the above relation, are recorded in Table 1, which are similar to the values of *K* calculated in experiment 1.

The relative order of stability of these metal-aspartate complexes at lower pH ranges was found to be Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II}. However, at higher pH ranges the Zn complexes were found to be a little more stable than the Co complexes.

Aspartic acid coordinates to the metal ions through two carboxyl groups and an amino group for the formation of neutral complexes. A proton from the coordinated water molecules may be dissociating for the formation of anionic complexes.

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Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XIII. Iron-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc- and Mercury-(II) Complexes with ONO Tridentate Schiff Bases

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A series of metal complexes containing salicylidene amino acids as ligands have been reported by Ray and Mukherjee¹. Dutta and Bhattacharya² prepared mixed chelates of salicylidene aminoacids and bidentate nitrogen donors². The present paper describes the synthesis of two dibasic ONO tridentate Schiff bases, acetophenone glycine and acetophenone alanine, and their complexation behaviour with Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Schiff bases acetophenone glycine (LH₂) and acetophenone alanine (L'H₂) were prepared by condensing *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (1.4 ml) in ethanol (50 ml) with glycine (0.75 g) and alanine (0.89 g) at ~100° respectively for about 1 h. The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing the Schiff bases with metal(II) chloride or acetate in the 1 : 1 ratio for about 0.5 h. After cooling, concentrated ammonia was added to it dropwise. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Elemental analysis and physicochemical measurements were done as described earlier³.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values (Δ_M) of all the complexes in DMF (5–10 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. In the ir spectra

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Mol. Wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % :	
			Found/(Calcd.)	M N
LH ₂	Yellow	182 (199)	—	6.89 (7.25)
L'H ₂	Light yellow	198 (207)	—	6.51 (6.76)
[Fe ₂ L ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Brown	545 (571)	20.21 (20.58)	4.58 (4.89)
[Fe ₂ L' ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Yellowish brown	566 (599)	19.46 (19.63)	4.31 (4.66)
[Co ₂ L ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Buff	546 (571)	20.24 (20.60)	4.57 (4.89)
[Co ₂ L' ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Reddish brown	563 (599)	19.48 (19.64)	4.32 (4.66)
[Ni ₂ L' ₂]	Red	458 (499)	23.17 (23.51)	5.41 (5.60)
[Ni ₂ L' ₂]	Red	509 (527)	21.98 (22.26)	5.16 (5.30)
[Cu ₂ L ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Blue	568 (581)	21.61 (21.86)	4.45 (4.81)
[Cu ₂ L' ₂ .4H ₂ O]	Greenish blue	589 (609)	20.52 (20.85)	4.26 (4.59)
[ZnL ₂]	White	418 (447)	14.27 (14.61)	6.07 (6.25)
[ZnL' ₂]	White	449 (475)	11.24 (11.63)	5.42 (5.89)
[HgL.H ₂ O]	Pale yellow	382 (409)	48.25 (48.97)	3.17 (3.41)
[HgL'.H ₂ O]	Yellow	397 (423)	47.02 (47.35)	3.10 (3.55)

*L=C₁₀H₉O₂N⁻², L'=C₁₁H₁₁O₂N⁻².

(KBr) the Schiff bases showed $\nu_{C=N}$ band at 1 590 (LH₂) and 1 595 cm⁻¹ (L'H₂). A hypsochromic shift of 5–15 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes indicate the bonding of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal ions⁴. The ligands show stretching frequencies at about 3 450 cm⁻¹ (OH) which appear at 3 100–3 350 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band (1 520 cm⁻¹) of free ligand was observed at 1 530

and 1 535 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating monodentate coordination of phenolic oxygen atom to the metal ions⁵. The ν_s and ν_{as} vibrations of the carboxylate group for the Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes (of LH₂) appear at about 1 540 and 1 430 and at about 1 470 and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (of L'H₂) respectively with a difference of about 110 cm⁻¹, suggestive of bidentate coordination of the carboxylate group. In case of the Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes, the frequency difference is ~155 cm⁻¹ indicating monodentate nature of the carboxylate group^{6,7}. The presence of coordinated water in the Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes was indicated by a broad band at ~3 400 cm⁻¹ followed by a sharp band at ~870 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively⁸ to stretching and rocking vibrations of OH moiety. The 450 and 510 cm⁻¹ bands are assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively.

A sharp endothermic peak on the DTA curve of the Co^{II} complex [Co₂L₂.4H₂O] suggests the loss of four water molecules at 240°.

Molecular weights of the Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes suggest dimeric nature of the complexes while those of Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes suggest monomeric species.

Electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes show three bands at ~8 600, ~18 000 and ~19 500 cm⁻¹ attributable⁹ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, suggesting for an octahedral configuration. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes were around 2.91 B.M. indicating magnetic interaction between the metal ions¹⁰. Two bands at 24 300 and 27 000 cm⁻¹ attributable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively, were observed for the nickel(II) complexes showing square-planar configuration, which is in conformity with the diamagnetic nature of the complexes. Sub-normal magnetic moment (1.2 B.M.) of the copper(II) complexes indicates the Cu–Cu interaction. The copper(II) complexes show one broad asymmetric band at ~13 150 cm⁻¹ suggesting a tetragonally distorted structure¹¹.

From the shape of the esr spectrum of Cu^{II}-LH₂ complex at the X-band, it is evident that the symmetry around Cu^{II} in the unit cell of the complex is tetragonal¹² (elongated octahedral), with $d_{z^2-y^2}$ ground state. The G value has been calculated to be 2.77. It is found that when this G value lies between 5.0 and 3.5, the g values will be near to molecular g values, and when they lie outside this range, the g values indicate strong exchange interaction among magnetically inequivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell. Since the G value for the present complex fall beyond this range, the g values indicate the existence of more than one magnetically inequivalent molecules with exchange interaction among Cu^{II} ions. Hence these g values represent the overall symmetry of these molecule in the unit cell¹³ (Table 2). The room temperature esr data (Table 2) indicate the existence of two species with axial symmetry.

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF $\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Band	g_{11}	g_1	G
X	2.230	2.083	2.77
Q	2.235(A)	2.074(A)	
	2.105(B)	2.075(B)	

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Polarographic Study of Complexation Behaviour of β -Resorcyaldehyde with some Transition Metal Cations in Aqueous Ethanol (70%) Media

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β -Resorcyaldehyde as a bidentate ligand is of special interest because of its use in the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions¹. Potentiometric studies² on complex formation of this ligand with Mn^{II} ,

Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} revealed stepwise formation of complexes. In the present study, polarographic examination of complexation of β -resorcyaldehyde with these cations has been carried out and stabilities of the complexes have been determined by Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method³⁻⁵.

Experimental

A Polariter PO4g Radiometer polarograph at a chart speed of 2 cm min^{-1} using a Sargent capillary with characteristics $m=1.068 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=4.3 \text{ s}$ for 70 cm mercury head at constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$) was used to record the polarograms. Nitrogen gas was bubbled to deaerate the solutions taken in a double-walled H-type cell with a built-in SCE in the second limb of the cell. pH was measured on an ELICO-LI-120 digital pH meter ($\pm 0.01 \text{ pH unit}$).

β -Resorcyaldehyde (m.p. 135–36°) (Bio-organics, India) was used. The metal perchlorates were prepared from the respective oxides, hydroxides, carbonates or nitrates. The ligand solution (1.0 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared in aldehyde-free ethanol.

Test solutions contained (a) metal ion (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), ethanol (7.0 ml), gelatin (0.25 ml; 0.2%), made up to 10 ml with double-distilled water and (b) metal ion (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}), LiClO_4 (1.0 ml, 1.0 mol dm^{-3}), gelatin (0.25 ml, 0.2%), increasing volumes of ligand in ethanol, additional ethanol to make up to 7 ml and water to make up to 10 ml, after adjusting pH with perchloric acid or lithium hydroxide, as required.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic characteristic data are presented in Table 1. The polarograms are all well-defined diffusion-controlled cathodic waves with slopes 45, 50, 55 and 60 mV for the respective metal-ligand systems

The decrease in diffusion currents ($\Delta \bar{i}_d$) is plotted against $\log [L]$ and the sigmoidal pseudo-formation curve was integrated according to Fronaeus⁶ to provide $F'_0[L]$ data at each ligand concentration. These values are then plotted

TABLE 1—COMPLEXATION OF M(II) IONS WITH β -RESORCYALDEHYDE IN 70% (ETHANOL-WATER) MEDIA AT pH's 6.55, 7.77, 6.92, 4.87 AND 8.71 RESPECTIVELY

$m=1.068 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=4.3 \text{ s}$, $h=70 \text{ cm}$, $\text{temp.}=298 \text{ K}$

[L] mol dm^{-3}	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Mn})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Mn})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Co})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Co})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Ni})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Ni})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Cu})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Cu})$ μ_A	$-E_{1/2}(\text{Zn})$ V	$\bar{i}_d(\text{Zn})$ μ_A
0.00000	1.32	3.29	1.33	1.19	1.10	1.58	0.02	3.89	1.20	2.77
0.00001	1.33	3.28	1.34	0.93	1.11	1.33	0.03	3.59	1.21	2.45
0.00005	1.34	3.26	1.36	0.89	1.12	1.32	0.05	3.55	1.22	2.43
0.0001	1.36	3.23	1.37	0.87	1.14	1.30	0.07	3.53	1.23	2.41
0.0005	1.38	3.19	1.38	0.83	1.16	1.26	0.08	3.49	1.24	2.37
0.0010	1.40	3.17	1.40	0.79	1.18	1.24	0.09	3.47	1.26	2.35
0.0020	1.42	3.15	1.42	0.75	1.19	1.22	0.10	3.45	1.28	2.31
0.0050	1.43	3.11	1.44	0.73	1.21	1.18	0.12	3.43	1.30	2.23

$\log \beta_2(\text{Mn})=6.78$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Co})=8.07$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Ni})=8.60$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Cu})=9.23$, $\log \beta_2(\text{Zn})=7.79$.